

1 **Deletion of CYLD in regulatory T cells results in modulation of genes that are component**
2 **elements of the exhaustion and senescence programs.**

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12 Citations

13 1. Trompouki, E., Hatzivassiliou, E., Tschritzis, T., Farmer, H., Ashworth, A. and Mosialos, G., 2003.
14 CYLD is a deubiquitinating enzyme that negatively regulates NF- κ B activation by TNFR family members.
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